

ON THE FINITENESS OF CARMICHAEL NUMBERS WITH
FERMAT FACTORS AND $L = 2^\alpha P^2$.

Yu Tsumura

puremaaath@gmail.com

Received: 10/3/17, Revised: 6/12/19, Accepted: 6/9/20, Published: 6/18/20

Abstract

Let m be a Carmichael number and let L be the least common multiple of $p - 1$, where p runs over the prime factors of m . We determine all the Carmichael numbers m with a known Fermat prime factor such that $L = 2^\alpha P^2$, where $\alpha \in \mathbb{N}$ and P is an odd prime number. There are eleven such Carmichael numbers.

1. Introduction

Fermat's little theorem states that a prime number p divides $a^p - a$ for any $a \in \mathbb{N}$. It would be interesting if prime numbers are the only integers (except for 1) having this property. Some composites m , however, satisfies $a^m \equiv a \pmod{m}$ for all integers a . Such a composite is called a *Carmichael number*. The smallest Carmichael number is 561 and it was found by Carmichael in 1910 [2]. Prior to Carmichael's discovery, Korselt [4] had provided the following simple test for Carmichael numbers in 1899:

(Korselt's criterion). *A composite m is a Carmichael number if and only if m is squarefree and $p - 1$ divides $m - 1$ for all prime divisors p of m .*

Let $L = L_m$ be the least common multiple of $p_i - 1$, where $m = p_1 \cdots p_n$ is the prime decomposition of a squarefree composite. Then Korselt's criterion can be rephrased as follows: m is a Carmichael number if and only if $L \mid m - 1$.

It is known that there are infinitely many Carmichael numbers. The result was proved by Alfred, Granville, and Pomerance in 1994 [1] based on Erdős' heuristic argument [3]. The idea is to construct an integer L' so that it is divisible by $p - 1$ for a large number of primes p . Then if the product $m = p_1 \cdots p_k$ of some of these primes is congruent to 1 modulo L' , then m is a Carmichael number by Korselt's criterion since we have $L_m \mid L' \mid m - 1$. [1] showed that in fact there are infinitely many such L' and such products, hence the infinitude of Carmichael numbers follows. Wright noted that as L' contains a sizable number of prime factors, it is likely that L_m corresponding to the Carmichael numbers m obtained in this manner contains

many prime factors as well. This led him the study of Carmichael numbers with restricted L . Wright [5] proved that there are no Carmichael numbers with $L = 2^\alpha$ and determined all the Carmichael numbers with $L = 2^\alpha P$ for some odd prime P under the assumption that the Fermat primes conjecture is true. Assuming that 3, 5, 17, 257, and 65537 are the only Fermat primes, there are only eight Carmichael numbers with $L = 2^\alpha P$, and P is one of 3, 5, 7 or 127. The prime factorizations of these numbers are given in [5].

In this article, we extend Wright’s result to the next simplest case $L = 2^\alpha P^2$. Let m be a Carmichael number with $L = 2^\alpha P^2$. Then each prime factor of m is one of the primes of the form $p = 2^k + 1$, $q = 2^l P + 1$, or $r = 2^s P^2 + 1$. (We call these prime factors *Type 1*, *Type 2*, and *Type 3* primes, respectively.) We assume that m is divisible by at least one of the known Fermat prime numbers. Under this assumption, we prove the following theorem.

Theorem 1. *Let m be a Carmichael number with $L = 2^\alpha P^2$ for some odd prime P . Suppose that m is divisible by one of the known Fermat primes and not divisible by any Fermat prime not yet known. Then m must be one of the following 11 Carmichael numbers. In particular, P is either 5 or 3.*

$3 \cdot 11 \cdot 17 \cdot 401 \cdot 641 \cdot 1601$	$L = 2^2 \cdot 5^2$
$5 \cdot 7 \cdot 17 \cdot 19 \cdot 73$	$L = 2^4 \cdot 3^2$
$5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 73 \cdot 97 \cdot 257$	$L = 2^8 \cdot 3^2$
$5 \cdot 13 \cdot 257 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153$	$L = 2^8 \cdot 3^2$
$5 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 257 \cdot 577 \cdot 769$	$L = 2^8 \cdot 3^2$
$5 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 193 \cdot 257 \cdot 1153$	$L = 2^8 \cdot 3^2$
$5 \cdot 13 \cdot 257 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153 \cdot 18433$	$L = 2^{11} \cdot 3^2$
$5 \cdot 257 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 577 \cdot 12289 \cdot 18433$	$L = 2^{12} \cdot 3^2$
$5 \cdot 7 \cdot 13 \cdot 19 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 193 \cdot 257 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153$	$L = 2^8 \cdot 3^2$
$5 \cdot 7 \cdot 13 \cdot 19 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 257 \cdot 577 \cdot 769 \cdot 1153$	$L = 2^8 \cdot 3^2$
$5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 73 \cdot 97 \cdot 193 \cdot 577 \cdot 769 \cdot 12289 \cdot 147457 \cdot 65537 \cdot 1179649 \cdot 786433$	$L = 2^{18} \cdot 3^2$

In Section 2, we review a theorem (Theorem 2) that played an important role in [5] and will be used extensively in this article in a slightly extended form (Theorem 3). Suppose that $n = 2^\beta x + 1$ is an integer, where x is odd. Then we call the exponent β of 2 the *2-power* of n . Theorem 2 proves that if a Carmichael number is expressed as the product of several odd integers, then there cannot be a unique smallest 2-power among these integers.

Several lemmas will be given in Section 3 that narrow down the number of possible primes P . In particular, we will see that a Carmichael number under our assumption must have at least two Fermat primes, and P is a divisor of $R - 1$, where R is the product of Fermat prime factors of m .

Section 4 provides a general procedure to obtain all Carmichael numbers for a given P . Theorem 3, which will be referred to as the minimality argument, implies the existence of some prime factor or a pair of prime factors of a Carmichael number with relatively small 2-power. As there are not so many possible such prime numbers or pairs, the procedure terminates and produces all Carmichael number for P , or proves that there are no Carmichael numbers for P .

By Theorem 2, at least two of the smallest 2-powers of Type 1, 2, and 3 primes must be the same. Hence there are three cases to consider according to which two 2-powers are the same.

The rest of the paper will be devoted to a careful scrutiny of Carmichael numbers in these three cases.

2. General Results on Carmichael Numbers

Let m be a Carmichael number. Let L be the least common multiple of $p - 1$, where p runs over the prime factors of m . Korselt's criterion yields that L divides $m - 1$.

The following result is crucial, which is proved in [5, Theorem 2.1]. For completeness, we give its proof.

Theorem 2. *Let m be a Carmichael number and write*

$$m = \prod_{i=1}^n (2^{\alpha_i} D_i + 1),$$

where D_i are odd integers, $n \geq 2$, and $\alpha_1 \leq \alpha_2 \leq \dots \leq \alpha_n$. Then if $2^{\alpha_1+1} \mid L$, then $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2$.

Proof. Seeking a contradiction, assume that $\alpha_1 < \alpha_2$. Then we have

$$m = \prod_{i=1}^n (2^{\alpha_i} D_i + 1) \equiv 2^{\alpha_1} D_1 + 1 \pmod{2^{\alpha_1+1}}.$$

Since $2^{\alpha_1+1} \mid L$ by assumption and $L \mid m - 1$ by Korselt's criterion, we obtain

$$m \equiv 1 \pmod{2^{\alpha_1+1}}.$$

It follows that

$$2^{\alpha_1} D_1 + 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{2^{\alpha_1+1}}.$$

However, this implies that D_1 is even, which contradicts that D_1 is odd. Thus, we have $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2$. □

Observe that Theorem 2 does not assume that each factor $2^{\alpha_i} D_i + 1$ to be prime.

3. Lemmas

In this section, we prove several lemmas that reduce the possible factors of Carmichael numbers.

Let m be a Carmichael number. Let L be the least common multiple of $p - 1$, where p runs over the prime factors of m . In this paper, we assume that

$$L = 2^\alpha P^2,$$

where $\alpha \in \mathbb{N}$ and P is an odd prime number. This implies that each of the prime factors of m is one of the followings:

$p = 2^k + 1$	Type 1 (Fermat's prime)
$q = 2^l P + 1$	Type 2
$r = 2^s P^2 + 1$	Type 3.

We further assume that m has at least one Type 1 prime factor.

From now on, we reserve the letters p, q, r (and the versions with subscripts p_i, q_i, r_i) for Type 1, 2, 3 primes, respectively. Similarly we reserve letters k, l, s for the exponent of 2 in these prime numbers.

Lemma 1. *Let P be an odd prime number. Suppose that $2^k + 1$, $2^l P + 1$, and $2^s P^2 + 1$ are prime numbers. Then:*

1. k is a power of 2.
2. If $P \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, then l is even.
3. If $P \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, then l is odd.
4. If $P \neq 3$, then s is even.

Let $t = 2^a x + 1$ be a prime number, where x is an odd integer. Then we say that t is an a -prime. A pair (t_1, t_2) of a -prime numbers is called a -pair.

Corollary 1. *With the notation of Lemma 1, when $P \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, there is no a -pair between Type 2 and Type 3 primes for any integer a .*

In the next lemma, a Carmichael number m might or might not have Type 1 prime factors.

Lemma 2. *Let m be a Carmichael number with $L = 2^\alpha P^2$. Suppose that m is not of the form $p_1 q_1 r_1$ with $k_1 = l_1 = s_1$. If $P \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, then $P \not\equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.*

Proof. Let

$$m = \prod_{i \geq 1} v_i,$$

where v_i is a prime of Type 1, 2, or 3. Note that any Carmichael number has three or more prime factors. Let β_i be the 2-power of v_i and suppose that $0 < \beta_1 \leq \beta_2 \leq \beta_3 \leq \dots$. Observe that $\beta_1 = \beta_2$ by Theorem 2 because of the assumption of the shape of m . Suppose that $P \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. Then both l_i and s_i are even by Lemma 1. Hence $k_1 \neq 1$, otherwise k_1 is the unique smallest power of 2 and this contradicts Theorem 2. So each k_i is even, and hence every β_i is even. Let

$$v_i = 2^{\beta_i} P^{\delta_i} + 1,$$

where $\delta_i = 0, 1, 2$ depending on the type of v_i . Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} v_1 v_2 &= (2^{\beta_1} P^{\delta_1} + 1)(2^{\beta_1} P^{\delta_2} + 1) \\ &= 2^{2\beta_1} P^{\delta_1 + \delta_2} + 2^{\beta_1} P^{\delta_1} + 2^{\beta_1} P^{\delta_2} + 1 \\ &= 2^{\beta_1} (2^{\beta_1} P^{\delta_1 + \delta_2} + P^{\delta_1} + P^{\delta_2}) + 1. \end{aligned}$$

Now seeking a contradiction, assume that $P \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$. Then we have

$$2^{\beta_1} P^{\delta_1 + \delta_2} + P^{\delta_1} + P^{\delta_2} \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$$

since β_1 is even. It follows that the 2-power of $v_1 v_2$ is $\beta_1 + 1$.

Then consider the expression

$$m = (v_1 v_2) \prod_{i \geq 3} v_i.$$

If $\beta_1 < \beta_3$, then $\beta_3 \geq \beta_1 + 2$ as each β_i is even. Thus $2^{\beta_1+2} | L$ and 2^{β_1+1} is the unique smallest power of 2 in the above expression of m . This contradicts Theorem 2. Hence $\beta_3 = \beta_1$. Then we have $v_1 v_2 v_3 = p_1 q_1 r_1$ with $k_1 = l_1 = s_1$, and by assumption that $m \neq p_1 q_1 r_1$, there exists v_4 with $\beta_4 \geq \beta_1 + 2$. Then in the expression

$$m = v_3 (v_1 v_2) \prod_{i \geq 4} v_i,$$

v_3 has the unique smallest power β_1 of 2, and $2^{\beta_1+1} | 2^{\beta_4} | L$. This contradicts Theorem 2. Hence we conclude that $P \not\equiv 1 \pmod{4}$. \square

3.1. Fermat Primes and the Prime P

Lemma 3. *Let m be a Carmichael number with $L = 2^\alpha P^2$. Let p_1, \dots, p_n be the Type 1 prime divisors of m . Then*

$$p_1 \cdots p_n \equiv 1 \pmod{P}.$$

Proof. By Korselt's criterion, we have $P | L | m - 1$. It follows that

$$1 \equiv m \equiv p_1 \cdots p_n \pmod{P}$$

since Type 2 and Type 3 primes are congruent to 1 modulo P . \square

Corollary 2. *Let m be a Carmichael number with $L = 2^\alpha P^2$. Assume that m has a Type 1 (Fermat) prime factor. Then m has at least two distinct Fermat prime factors.*

Proof. If there is a unique Type 1 divisor $p_1 = 2^{k_1} + 1$ of m , then Lemma 3 yields that

$$p_1 = 2^{k_1} + 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{P}.$$

Thus $P \mid 2^{k_1}$ and this is impossible because P is an odd prime. □

For the rest of the paper, we assume that m is a Carmichael number with $L = 2^\alpha P^2$ and m has a Type 1 factor. Also we restrict Type 1 factors to be known Fermat’s primes: $p_i = 3, 5, 17, 257, 65537$.

By Lemma 3 and Corollary 2, the prime P appears in the prime factorization of $R - 1$, where R is the product of two or more known Fermat’s primes.

Table 1 can be found in [5, Table 1], though we rearranged the table by k_1 .

3.2. Cases

Let m be a Carmichael number with $L = 2^\alpha P^2$ and write

$$m = \left(\prod_{i=1}^{n_1} p_i \right) \left(\prod_{i=1}^{n_2} q_i \right) \left(\prod_{i=1}^{n_3} r_i \right) = \left(\prod_{i=1}^{n_1} 2^{k_i} + 1 \right) \left(\prod_{i=1}^{n_2} 2^{l_i} P + 1 \right) \left(\prod_{i=1}^{n_3} 2^{s_i} P^2 + 1 \right)$$

with $k_1 < k_2 < \dots < k_{n_1}$, $l_1 < l_2 < \dots < l_{n_2}$, and $s_1 < s_2 < \dots < s_{n_3}$. We are assuming $n_1 \geq 1$. By Theorem 2, there cannot be a unique smallest 2-power. Thus, there are three cases to consider.

Case A $k_1 = l_1 \leq s_1$.

Case B $k_1 = s_1 < l_1$.

Case C $l_1 = s_1 < k_1$.

We also consider the case when m has no Type 2 factor in Case B.

4. Procedure

The next theorem will play a key role in our procedure to find Carmichael numbers. This theorem holds for any Carmichael number.

Theorem 3 (The minimality argument). *Let m be a Carmichael number. Suppose that $2^a \mid L$ for some $a \in \mathbb{N}$. Write*

$$m = (2^b x + 1)(2^{b_1} x_1 + 1) \cdots (2^{b_f} x_f + 1) \prod_{i=1}^g v_i,$$

Table 1: Products of Fermat primes

Combination of Primes (R)	Factorization of $R - 1$	k_1
$3 * 5$	$2 * 7$	1
$3 * 17$	$2 * 5^2$	1
$3 * 257$	$2 * 5 * 7 * 11$	1
$3 * 65537$	$2 * 5 * 19661$	1
$3 * 5 * 17$	$2 * 127$	1
$3 * 5 * 257$	$2 * 41 * 47$	1
$3 * 17 * 257$	$2 * 6553$	1
$3 * 5 * 65537$	$2 * 491527$	1
$3 * 17 * 65537$	$2 * 127 * 13159$	1
$3 * 257 * 65537$	$2 * 25264513$	1
$3 * 5 * 17 * 257$	$2 * 7 * 31 * 151$	1
$3 * 5 * 257 * 65537$	$2 * 7 * 18046081$	1
$3 * 5 * 17 * 65537$	$2 * 8355967$	1
$3 * 17 * 257 * 65537$	$2 * 19 * 22605091$	1
$3 * 5 * 17 * 257 * 65537$	$2 * 2147483647$	1
$5 * 17$	$2^2 * 3 * 7$	2
$5 * 257$	$2^2 * 3 * 107$	2
$5 * 65537$	$2^2 * 3 * 7 * 47 * 83$	2
$5 * 17 * 257$	$2^2 * 43 * 127$	2
$5 * 17 * 65537$	$2^2 * 131 * 10631$	2
$5 * 257 * 65537$	$2^2 * 467 * 45083$	2
$5 * 17 * 257 * 65537$	$2^2 * 3 * 7 * 11 * 31 * 151 * 331$	2
$17 * 257$	$2^4 * 3^3 * 7 * 13$	4
$17 * 65537$	$2^4 * 3^3 * 2579$	4
$17 * 257 * 65537$	$2^4 * 29 * 43 * 113 * 127$	4
$257 * 65537$	$2^8 * 3 * 7 * 13 * 241$	8

where x, x_1, \dots, x_f are odd integers, v_i is a prime factor of m , and $g \geq 1$. Let β_i be the 2-power of v_i . That is, $2^{\beta_i} D + 1 = v_i$ for some odd D . Assume that

$$b < b_1 \leq b_2 \leq \dots \leq b_f \text{ and } \beta_1 \leq \beta_2 \leq \dots \leq \beta_g.$$

1. If $b < a$, then v_1 is a b -prime or (v_1, v_2) is a β_1 -pair with $\beta_1 < b$.
2. If $b \geq a$, then either v_1 is a β_1 -prime with $a \leq \beta_1 \leq b$ or we have a β_1 -pair (v_1, v_2) with $\beta_1 < a$.

Proof. 1. Since $b < a$, we have $2^{b+1} \mid 2^a \mid L$. It follows from Theorem 2 that b cannot be the unique smallest 2-power. Thus, we have the following possibilities: $b = \beta_1$ or $\beta_1 = \beta_2 < b$ by Theorem 2. The first case yield that v_1 is a b -prime. The second case implies that (v_1, v_2) is a β_1 -pair and $\beta_1 < b$.

2. Assume that $\beta_1 > b$. Then we have $2^{b+1} \mid 2^{\beta_1} \mid L$. This implies that b is the unique smallest 2-power, which contradicts Theorem 2. Thus we have $\beta_1 \leq b$.
 If $\beta_1 < a$, then as $\beta_1 < a \leq b$ we must have $\beta_1 = \beta_2$ to avoid a unique smallest 2-power. Thus, in this case we have a β_1 -pair (v_1, v_2) . □

We explain the procedure to find all Carmichael numbers for a given P . In the sequel, we use the letter x to denote an odd number but its actual value could be different in each occurrence. For example, we write

$$5 \cdot 13 = (2^2x + 1)(2^2x + 1) = 2^6x + 1.$$

In this case, the actual values are $x = 1, 3, 1$ in this order.

Let us fix P . Then each of Case A, B, C, we start with two prime numbers with minimal 2-power together with Type 1 primes that give P . Let a be the largest integer among the a -prime factors of these known factors of m . Then $2^a \mid L$.

Step 1 We multiply some or all of these known factors and find the decomposition of the form $(2^{a_1}x + 1) \cdots (2^{a_n}x + 1)$, with $a_1 < a_2 \leq a_3 \leq \cdots \leq a_n$. It is possible that we have only one term. Then a Carmichael number is of the form

$$m = (2^{a_1}x + 1) \cdots (2^{a_n}x + 1) \prod v_i,$$

where v_i are primes of Type 1, 2, 3, or the product could be empty.

Step 2 Check whether $(2^{a_1}x + 1) \cdots (2^{a_n}x + 1)$ is a Carmichael number by Korselt's criterion. If the product $\prod_{i \geq 1} v_i$ from Step 1 is not empty, then it must contain a prime number or a pair of prime numbers satisfying some condition by the minimality argument (Theorem 3). There are only finitely many possible cases.

Step 3 We multiply some or all of the factors we obtained in Step 1 and Step 2. Then we have

$$m = (2^{b_1}x + 1) \cdots (2^{b_f}x + 1) \prod v_i,$$

where v_i can be a prime of Type 1, 2, 3 that did not appear in Step 1 and Step 2 (recall that every Carmichael number is squarefree), or the product $\prod v_i$ could be empty.

We repeat Step 2 and 3 until there is no possible prime or a pair of primes in Step 2.

We remark that there is no theoretical guarantee that this process terminates. However, our computation below terminates after a finite number of steps.

5. Case A: $k_1 = l_1 \leq s_1$.

We classify Carmichael numbers with $k_1 = l_1 \leq s_1$ in this section. We reduce the number of the possible P from Table 1 by removing those (P, k_1) such that $2^{k_1}P + 1$ are not prime. The possible primes are

Table 2: After removing composite $2^{k_1}P + 1$

Combination of Primes (R)	Possible factors P of $R - 1$	k_1
$3 * 17$	5	1
$3 * 257$	5, 11	1
$3 * 65537$	5, 19661	1
$3 * 5 * 257$	41	1
$5 * 17$	3, 7	2
$5 * 257$	3	2
$5 * 65537$	3, 7	2
$5 * 17 * 257$	43, 127	2
$5 * 17 * 257 * 65537$	3, 7	2

$$P = 3, 5, 7, 11, 41, 43, 127, 19661.$$

In the sequel, we actually prove that none of these produces a Carmichael number except for $P = 3, 5$.

5.1. The Impossible Case: $P = 43$

As in [5], let us start with 43. We prove that there is no Carmichael number with $P = 43$. This case illustrates the procedure explained in Section 4.

Let m be a Carmichael number with $L = 2^\alpha \cdot 43^2$. Since $P = 43$, the product of Type 1 primes must be $5 \cdot 17 \cdot 257$ from Table 2.

Since $k_1 = l_1 = 2$ (recall we are dealing with Case A), we have

$$q_1 = 2^2 \cdot 43 + 1 = 173.$$

Let

$$m = 5 \cdot 17 \cdot 257 \cdot 173 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i,$$

where u_i is either a Type 2 or Type 3 prime (and there must be at least one Type 3 prime.) Note that $2^8 \mid L$. Then we find the decomposition

$$m = (2^4 + 1)(2^5 \cdot 27 + 1)(2^8 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i.$$

By the minimality argument (Theorem 3), there exists a pair (u_1, u_2) of Type 2 and Type 3 primes with 2-power less than 4 (we call such a pair n -pair with

$n < 4$), or there exists u_1 of Type 2 or Type 3 with 2-power 4 (we call such a prime *4-prime*). Since $k_1 = l_1 = 2$ is already used, the 2-power of a pair must be greater than 2 and less than 4. Thus the 2-power of a pair must be 3. However, since $43 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, we know l_i is even by Lemma 1. So there is no such pair.

Note that the numbers

$$2^4 \cdot 43 + 1 = 13 \cdot 53 \text{ and } 2^4 \cdot 43^2 + 1 = 5 \cdot 61 \cdot 97$$

are composite. So there is no 4-prime of Type 2 or 3. We have proved the following result.

Theorem 4. *If $P = 43$, then there is no Carmichael number in Case A.*

5.2. The Impossible Case: $P = 19661$

Let us next consider the case $P = 19661$. From Table 2, the product of Type 1 primes is $3 \cdot 65537$ and $k_1 = 1$. Since $k_1 = l_1 = 1$, we have $q_1 = 2 \cdot 19661 + 1 = 39323$. Let

$$m = 3 \cdot 65537 \cdot 39323 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i,$$

where u_i is a prime of Type 2 or Type 3. Note that $2^{16} \mid L$ and $P \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, hence l_i is odd by Lemma 1. We have

$$m = (2^4 \cdot 7373 + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i.$$

By the minimality argument and Corollary 1, there is no pair (u_1, u_2) of Type 2 and 3, and there must be a 4-prime of Type 2 or 3 (and this should be Type 3 as l_i is odd). As the number $2^4 \cdot 19661^2 + 1 = 3217 \cdot 1922561$ is composite, there is no 4-prime as well. This proves:

Theorem 5. *If $P = 19661$, then there is no Carmichael number for Case A.*

5.3. The Impossible Case: $P = 41$

If $P = 41$, then the product of Type 1 primes is $3 \cdot 5 \cdot 257$ from Table 2 and $k_1 = l_1 = 1$. So $q_1 = 2 \cdot 41 + 1 = 83$. Note $2^8 \mid L$ and $P \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, hence l_i is odd. Let

$$m = 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 83 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i,$$

where u_i is a prime of Type 2 or Type 3. Then we have

$$m = (2^2 + 1)(2^3 \cdot 31 + 1)(2^8 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i.$$

Consider the minimality argument. By Corollary 1, there is no available pair (u_1, u_2) . Since l_i is odd, the only candidate for 2-prime is the Type 3 2-prime. However, the number $2^2 \cdot 41^2 + 1 = 5^2 \cdot 269$ is not prime. Hence we have:

Theorem 6. *If $P = 41$, then there is no Carmichael number for Case A.*

5.4. The Impossible Case: $P = 11$

When $P = 11$, the product of Type 1 primes is $3 \cdot 257$ from Table 2. Then we have $k_1 = l_1 = 1$, and thus $q_1 = 2 \cdot 11 + 1 = 23$. Using $\prod_{i \geq 1} u_i$ as in the previous cases, we have

$$m = 3 \cdot 257 \cdot 23 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i = (2 \cdot 17 + 1)(2^8 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i.$$

Since s_1 is even by Lemma 1, there is no 1-prime among u_i . Thus, 2^1 is the unique smallest power and $2^8 \mid L$. We conclude that m cannot be a Carmichael number in this case. So we have:

Theorem 7. *If $P = 11$, then there is no Carmichael number for Case A.*

6. The Impossible Case: $P = 7$

We still assume $k_1 = l_1$ (Case A) and prove that there is no Carmichael number with $P = 7$. From Table 2, there are three possibilities for the Type 1 primes:

$$5 \cdot 17, \quad 5 \cdot 65537, \quad 5 \cdot 17 \cdot 257 \cdot 65537.$$

In any case, $k_1 = l_1 = 2$, and thus $q_1 = 2^2 \cdot 7 + 1 = 29$.

Let us first deal with the case when 17 divides m .

6.1. Case 1: 17 Divides m .

Suppose that 17 divides m . Let

$$m = 5 \cdot 17 \cdot 29 \prod_{i \geq 1} v_i = (2^5 \cdot 77 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} v_i,$$

where v_i is a prime of Type 1, 2, or 3. The only possible Type 1 primes for v_i are 257 and 65537. Note that $2^4 \mid L$. By the minimality argument (Theorem 3), either we must have an n -pair (v_1, v_2) with $n < 4$, or an n -prime with $n = 4$ or $n = 5$. Table 3 lists data of the numbers of the form $2^l \cdot 7 + 1$, $2^s \cdot 7^2 + 1$, and $2^k + 1$. Note that since $7 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, both l_i, s_i are even by Lemma 1. From the table, we see that there is no such pair. As 17 is already used, we have a unique 4-prime: 113.

Hence we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 17 \cdot 29 \cdot 113 \prod_{i \geq 2} v_i = (2^4 \cdot 3 \cdot 7 \cdot 829 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 2} v_i.$$

Since the product still must contain a Type 3 prime, it is not empty. By the minimality argument, there must be an n -pair with $n < 4$ or 4-prime, but this is impossible from Table 3 as there is no more 4-primes.

Table 3: Primality for $2^l \cdot 7 + 1, 2^s \cdot 7^2 + 1, 2^k + 1$

n	$2^n \cdot 7 + 1$	$2^n \cdot 7^2 + 1$	$2^n + 1$
2	29 prime	197 prime	5 prime
4	113 prime	×	17 prime
6	449 prime	3137 prime	×
8	×	×	257 prime
10	×	50177 prime	×
12	×	×	×
14	114689 prime	×	×
16	×	×	65537

×=composite, $7 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$

6.2. Case 2: 17 Does Not Divide m .

Suppose that m is not divisible by 17. Namely, the case when the type 1 combination is $5 \cdot 65537$. Then we have $k_1 = l_1 = 2$, and $q_1 = 2^2 \cdot 7 + 1 = 29$. Let

$$m = 5 \cdot 65537 \cdot 29 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i,$$

where u_i is a prime of Type 2 or 3. We have $2^{16} \mid L$. Then

$$m = (2^4 \cdot 9 + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i.$$

From Table 3, we see that there is no pair of u_i of 2-power smaller than 4. The only 4-prime u_1 is $q_2 = 113$ with $l_2 = 4$ (as we assume $17 \nmid m$). Since $5 \cdot 29 \cdot 113 = 2^{14} + 1$, we have

$$m = (2^{14} + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i$$

By the minimality argument, we must have either a pair (u_2, u_3) of Type 2 and 3 with 2-power between 5 and 13, or a 14-prime. From Table 3, we see that $(449, 3137)$ is a 6-pair and 114689 is a 14-prime.

6.2.1. Subcase 1: $(u_2, u_3) = (449, 3137)$

If $(u_2, u_3) = (449, 3137)$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 5 \cdot 65537 \cdot 29 \cdot 113 \cdot 449 \cdot 3137 \prod_{i \geq 4} u_i \\ &= (2^9 \cdot 45075167 + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 4} u_i. \end{aligned}$$

Since there is no 9-prime, and there is no n -pair for $7 \leq n \leq 8$ from Table 3, this case does not happen.

6.2.2. Subcase 2: $u_2 = q_3 = 114689$.

If $u_2 = q_3 = 114689$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 5 \cdot 65537 \cdot 29 \cdot 113 \cdot 114689 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i \\ &= (2^{16} + 1)(2^{17} \cdot 3^5 \cdot 59 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i. \end{aligned}$$

There is no 16-prime in Table 3. The only n -pair with $n < 16$ is (449, 3137) but we dealt with this case in Subcase 1. Thus, there is no Carmichael numbers for Case 2 as well. This completes the proof of:

Theorem 8. *If $P = 7$, then there is no Carmichael number for Case A.*

7. The Impossible Case: $P = 127$

Next, we prove that there is no Carmichael number when $P = 127$ for $k_1 = l_1 \leq s_1$ (Case A).

From Table 2, there is only one Type 1 combination: $5 \cdot 17 \cdot 257$ with $k_1 = l_1 = 2$. So we have $q_1 = 2^2 \cdot 127 + 1 = 509$. Let

$$m = 5 \cdot 17 \cdot 257 \cdot 509 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i = (2^9 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 19 \cdot 127 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i,$$

where u_i is a prime of Type 2 or Type 3. We have $2^8 \mid L$. Since $P = 127 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, we know that l_i, s_i are even. By the minimality argument (Theorem 3), there is an n -pair with $n < 8$ or an n -prime with $n = 8$ or $n = 9$. From Table 4, we see that there is no such n -pair or n -prime. Thus, m cannot be a Carmichael number.

Table 4: Primality for $2^l \cdot 127 + 1, 2^s \cdot 127^2 + 1$

n	$2^n \cdot 127 + 1$	$2^n \cdot 127^2 + 1$
2	509 prime	×
4	×	×
6	×	×
8	×	×
10	×	×
12	520193 prime	×
14	×	×
16	×	×

×=composite, $127 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$

Thus we obtain:

Theorem 9. *If $P = 127$, then there is no Carmichael number for Case A.*

8. Case: $P = 5$

The combinations of Type 1 primes for $P = 5$ are the following three from Table 2:

$$3 \cdot 17, \quad 3 \cdot 257, \quad 3 \cdot 65537.$$

So in any case, we have $k_1 = l_1 = 1$, and hence $q_1 = 2 \cdot 5 + 1 = 11$. Since $P = 5 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, we know that l_i is odd and s_i is even. In all cases, we have $2^4 \mid L$.

Let

$$m = 3 \cdot 11 \prod_{i \geq 1} v_i = (2^5 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} v_i,$$

where each v_i is a prime of Type 1, 2, or 3. If v_i is a Type 1 prime, then it must be one of 17, 257, 65537.

Table 5: Primality for $2^l \cdot 5 + 1, 2^s \cdot 5^2 + 1$

n	$2^n \cdot 5 + 1$	$2^n \cdot 5^2 + 1$	$2^n + 1$
1	11 prime	×	3 prime
2	×	101 prime	5 prime
3	41 prime	×	×
4	×	401 prime	17 prime
5	×	×	×

×=composite, $5 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$

As $2^4 \mid L$, by the minimality argument (Theorem 3), there must be an n -pair $n < 4$ or an n -prime for $n = 4, 5$. From Table 5, there is no such n -pair or 5-prime. There are two 4-primes: 401 and 17.

8.1. Case 1: $r_1 = 401$.

Let $r_1 = 401$. Then we have

$$m = 3 \cdot 11 \cdot 401 \prod_{i \geq 2} v_i = (2^4 \cdot 827 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 2} v_i.$$

By the minimality argument, there must be the other 4-prime 17. So we have

$$m = 3 \cdot 11 \cdot 17 \cdot 401 \prod_{i \geq 3} v_i = (2^6 \cdot 5 \cdot 19 \cdot 37 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} v_i.$$

There is no n -pair for $n < 4$ and there is no n -prime with $n = 4, 5$. Thus, we must have a unique 6-prime: 1601. So we have

$$m = 3 \cdot 11 \cdot 17 \cdot 401 \cdot 1601 \prod_{i \geq 4} v_i = (2^8 \cdot 5 \cdot 53 \cdot 5309 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 4} v_i.$$

By the minimality argument, we must have an n -prime with $n = 5, 6, 7, 8$. The only possible case is a 7-prime: 641. We have

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 3 \cdot 11 \cdot 17 \cdot 401 \cdot 1601 \cdot 641 \prod_{i \geq 5} v_i \\ &= (2^7 \cdot 5^2 \cdot 53 \cdot 72145063 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 5} v_i. \end{aligned}$$

If the product is empty, then

$$\boxed{3 \cdot 11 \cdot 17 \cdot 401 \cdot 641 \cdot 1601}$$

is a Carmichael number since $L = 2^7 \cdot 5^2$ divides $m - 1 = 2^7 \cdot 5^2 \cdot 53 \cdot 72145063$. In fact, the product must be empty since we used all n -pairs with $n < 4$ and n -primes for $4 \leq n \leq 7$.

8.2. Case 2: $p_2 = 17$.

Let us now consider the case $p_2 = 17$. Then we have

$$m = 3 \cdot 11 \cdot 17 \prod_{i \geq 2} v_i = (2^4 \cdot 5 \cdot +1) \prod_{i \geq 2} v_i.$$

Since there is no possible pair, we must have the other 4-prime: 401. Hence this case reduces to the previous case.

This proves:

Theorem 10. *When $P = 5$, there is exactly one Carmichael number m with $L = 2^\alpha \cdot 5^2$ in Case A. The factorization of m is given by*

$$m = 3 \cdot 11 \cdot 17 \cdot 401 \cdot 641 \cdot 1601.$$

9. Case: $P = 3$

In this section, we consider Case A ($k_1 = l_1 \leq s_1$) with $P = 3$. From Table 2, there are four combinations of Type 1 primes for $P = 3$:

$$5 \cdot 17, \quad 5 \cdot 257, \quad 5 \cdot 65537, \quad 5 \cdot 17 \cdot 257 \cdot 65537.$$

In any case, we have $k_1 = l_1 = 2$, and thus $q_1 = 2^2 \cdot 3 + 1 = 13$. We also have $2^4 \mid 2^{k_2} \mid L$. Recall that since $P = 3$, the exponents l_i, s_i cannot be restricted by their parities.

We first deal with $5 \cdot 17$ and $5 \cdot 17 \cdot 257 \cdot 65537$ together, and we consider the rest two cases individually.

9.1. Case 1: $17 \mid m$

Suppose that $17 \mid m$. Let

$$m = 5 \cdot 17 \cdot 13 \prod_{i \geq 1} v_i = (2^4 \cdot 3 \cdot 23 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} v_i,$$

where each v_i is a prime of Type 1, 2, or 3.

Table 6: Primality for $2^l \cdot 3 + 1$, $2^n \cdot 3^2 + 1$

n	$2^n \cdot 3 + 1$	$2^n \cdot 3^2 + 1$	$2^n + 1$
1	7 prime	19 prime	3 prime
2	13 prime	37 prime	5 prime
3	×	73 prime	×
4	×	×	17 prime
5	97 prime	×	×
6	193 prime	577 prime	×
7	×	1153 prime	×
8	769 prime	×	257 prime
9	×	×	×
10	×	×	×
11	×	18433 prime	×
12	12289 prime	×	×
13	×	×	×
14	×	147457 prime	×
15	×	×	×
16	×	×	65537 prime
17	×	1179649 prime	×
18	786433 prime	×	×
	×	×	×
30	3221225473 prime	×	×

×=composite

After removing the used primes from Table 6, we see that there is no n -pair with $2 \leq n < 4$. Also, since 17 is already used, there is no 4-prime. Thus, in this case there is no Carmichael number.

9.2. Case 2: Type 1 Combination is $5 \cdot 257$

We next consider the case when the Type 1 combination is $5 \cdot 257$. Let

$$m = 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 13 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i = (2^6 + 1)(2^8 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i,$$

where each u_i is a prime of Type 2 or 3. We have $2^8 \mid L$. By the minimality argument, we must have an n -pair with $n < 6$ or a 6-prime. From Table 6, we find that there is no n -pair with $n < 6$. There are two 6-primes: 193 and 577.

9.2.1. Subcase 1: $q_2 = 193$

Suppose that $q_2 = 193$ with $l_2 = 6$. Then we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 13 \cdot 193 \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i = (2^9 \cdot 3 \cdot 2099 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i.$$

By the minimality argument, there is either an n -pair $n < 8$ or an 8- or 9-prime. According to Table 6, we only have the 8-prime 769. Then

$$m = 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 13 \cdot 193 \cdot 769 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i = (2^8 \cdot 3 \cdot 102 \cdot 31963 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i.$$

There must be an n -pair with $n < 8$ or an 8-prime by the minimality argument. However, there is no such pair or 8-prime. Hence $q_2 \neq 193$.

9.2.2. Subcase 2: $r_1 = 577$

Suppose that $r_1 = 577$ with $s_1 = 6$. Then we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 13 \cdot 577 \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i = (2^7 \cdot 293 + 1)(2^8 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i.$$

It follows from the minimality arguments that we must have a 7-prime as there is no n -pair $n < 7$. Thus we have $r_2 = 1153$ with $s_2 = 7$, and

$$m = 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 13 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i = (2^{11} \cdot 3^2 \cdot 602947 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i.$$

If the product is empty, then

$$m = 5 \cdot 13 \cdot 257 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153$$

is a Carmichael number since $L = 2^8 \cdot 3^2$ divides $m - 1 = 2^{11} \cdot 3^2 \cdot 602947$. If the product is nonempty, then there is an n -prime with $n = 7, 8, 9, 10, 11$. From Table 6, there are two cases to consider: 8-prime 769 and 11-prime 18433.

9.2.2.1. Subsubcase 1: $q_2 = 769$. Suppose that $q_1 = 769$ with $l_2 = 8$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 13 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153 \cdot 769 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i \\ &= (2^8 \cdot 3 \cdot 2113 \cdot 5266441 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i. \end{aligned}$$

The product must be empty otherwise the minimality argument requires more n -pairs with $n < 8$ or 8-primes, but we used all relevant primes from Table 6. If the product is empty, then m is not a Carmichael number as $3^2 \nmid m - 1$.

9.2.2.2. Subsubcase 2: $r_3 = 18433$. Next, suppose that $r_3 = 18433$ with $s_3 = 11$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 13 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153 \cdot 18433 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i \\ &= (2^{13} \cdot 3^2 \cdot 11 \cdot 29 \cdot 8710127 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i. \end{aligned}$$

If the product is empty, then

$$m = 5 \cdot 13 \cdot 257 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153 \cdot 18433$$

is a Carmichael number since $L = 2^{11} \cdot 3^2$ divides $m - 1 = 2^{13} \cdot 3^2 \cdot 11 \cdot 29 \cdot 8710127$.

Suppose the product is nonempty. Since $2^{11} \mid L$, there is an n -prime with $n = 11, 12, 13$. The only remaining choice is the 12-prime 12289 and we have

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 13 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153 \cdot 18433 \cdot 12289 \prod_{i \geq 4} u_i \\ &= (2^{12} \cdot 3 \cdot 13477 \cdot 15201615259 \cdot 8710127 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 4} u_i. \end{aligned}$$

As there is no more 12-prime and possible pair, the product is empty. But then m is not a Carmichael number as $3^2 \nmid m - 1$.

In summary, there are exactly two Carmichael numbers

$$5 \cdot 13 \cdot 257 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153 \quad \text{and} \quad 5 \cdot 13 \cdot 257 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153 \cdot 18433$$

in Case 2.

9.3. Case 3: Type 1 Combination is 5 · 65537

Finally, we consider the case when the Type 1 combination is 5 · 65537. We have $q_1 = 2^2 \cdot 3 + 1 = 13$. Let

$$m = 5 \cdot 65537 \cdot 13 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i = (2^6 + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i,$$

where each u_i is a prime of Type 2 or 3. We have $2^{16} \mid L$.

By the minimality argument, the product $\prod_{i \geq 1} u_i$ must contain either an n -pair with $n < 5$ or a 6-prime. We see from Table 6 that there is no such pair. There are two 6-primes: 193 and 577. Now we consider these two cases individually.

9.3.1. Subcase 1: $q_2 = 193$

Let us consider the case $q_2 = 193$ with $l_2 = 6$. Then we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 65537 \cdot 13 \cdot 193 \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i = (2^8 \cdot 7^2 + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i.$$

As there is no available n -pair with $n < 7$, we must have an 8-prime: $q_3 = 769$ with $l_3 = 8$. Then we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 65537 \cdot 13 \cdot 193 \cdot 769 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i = (2^{10} \cdot 9421 + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i.$$

Since there is no available n -pair with $n < 10$ and there is no 10-prime for $\prod_{i \geq 3} u_i$, this case does not happen.

9.3.2. Subcase 1: $r_1 = 577$

Next, suppose that $r_1 = 577$ with $s_1 = 6$. Then we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 65537 \cdot 13 \cdot 577 \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i = (2^7 \cdot 293 + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i.$$

Note that $2^{16} \mid L$. By the minimality argument with Table 6 yields that the 7-prime 1153 must be used. Thus $r_2 = 1153$ with $s_2 = 7$, and we have

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 5 \cdot 65537 \cdot 13 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i \\ &= (2^8 \cdot 31 \cdot 5449 + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i. \end{aligned}$$

Again the minimality argument implies that there is an 8-prime. So $q_2 = 769$ with $l_2 = 8$, and we have

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 5 \cdot 65537 \cdot 13 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153 \cdot 769 \prod_{i \geq 4} u_i \\ &= (2^9 \cdot 11 \cdot 29 \cdot 97 \cdot 2099 + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 4} u_i. \end{aligned}$$

Since there is no available n -pair with $n < 8$ and there is no 9-prime from Table 6, m is not a Carmichael number in this case. In conclusion, we obtain:

Theorem 11. *Let m be a Carmichael number with $L = 2^\alpha 3^2$ for some $\alpha \in \mathbb{N}$. Assume that m has at least one known Fermat prime factor and $k_1 = l_1 \leq s_1$. Then m is one of the following two Carmichael numbers:*

$$\boxed{5 \cdot 13 \cdot 257 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153} \quad \text{and} \quad \boxed{5 \cdot 257 \cdot 13 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153 \cdot 18433}.$$

This exhausts all the possible $P = 3, 5, 7, 11, 41, 43, 127, 19661$, and we complete the classification of Carmichael numbers for Case A ($k_1 = l_1 \leq s_1$).

10. Case B: $k_1 = s_1 < l_1$

We next consider Case B. So we assume that $k_1 = s_1 < l_1$ if a Type 2 factor exists. If m has no Type 2 factor, then we simply assume that $k_1 = l_1$. The first step is to reduce the number of possible pairs (P, k_1) from Table 1. We remove those (P, k_1) such that $2^{k_1}P^2 + 1$ is not prime. Note that s_1 is even if $P \neq 3$ by Lemma 1. Thus, we remove all $(P, 1)$ from Table 1.

The pairs (P, k_1) such that $2^{k_1}P^2 + 1$ are prime numbers are

$$(P, k_1) = (3, 2), (7, 2), (47, 2), (29, 4).$$

We list all the possible pairs (P, k_1) together with combinations of Type 1 primes in Table 7.

Table 7: The possible pairs (P, k_1) for Case B

Combination of Type 1 primes	(P, k_1)
5 · 17	(3, 2), (7, 2)
5 · 257	(3, 2)
5 · 65537	(3, 2), (7, 2), (47, 2)
5 · 17 · 257 · 65537	(3, 2), (7, 2)
17 · 257 · 65537	(29, 4)

11. The Impossible Case: $P = 29$

Let us consider the case $P = 29$. We see from Table 7 that $17 \cdot 257 \cdot 65537$ is the only Type 1 combination for $P = 29$. Note that $2^{16} \mid L$. We have $k_1 = s_1 = 4$, and hence $r_1 = 2^4 \cdot 29^2 + 1 = 13457$. Let

$$m = 17 \cdot 257 \cdot 65537 \cdot 13457 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i,$$

where u_i is a prime of Type 2 or 3. We have

$$m = (2^5 \cdot 3 \cdot 2383 + 1)(2^8 + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i.$$

It follows from $P = 29 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ that l_i is odd and s_i is even. Since the parities of l_i and s_i are distinct, there is no n -pair for any n . (Note that there is no available Type 1 primes.) Since $2^{16} \mid L$, by the minimality argument, there is a 5-prime (and it must be a Type 2 prime). Thus we have $q_1 = 2^5 \cdot 29 + 1 = 929$ with $l_1 = 5$. Then

we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 m &= 17 \cdot 257 \cdot 65537 \cdot 13457 \cdot 929 \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i \\
 &= (2^6 \cdot 5^2 \cdot 19 \cdot 6991 + 1)(2^8 + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i
 \end{aligned}$$

Since $2^{16} \mid L$, the minimality argument requires a 6-prime. As 6 is even, the only possible 6-prime is of Type 3. However, the number $2^6 \cdot 29^2 + 1 = 5^2 \cdot 2153$ is composite. Thus we have:

Theorem 12. *If $P = 29$, then there is no Carmichael number for Case B.*

12. The Impossible Case: $P = 47$

We now consider the case $P = 47$. From Table 7, the Type 1 combination is $5 \cdot 65537$. So $k_1 = s_1 = 2$, and $r_1 = 2^2 \cdot 47^2 + 1 = 8837$. Let

$$m = 5 \cdot 65537 \cdot 8837 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i = (2^3 \cdot 3 \cdot 7 \cdot 263 + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i,$$

where u_i is a Type 2 or 3 prime.

Since $P = 47 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, Corollary 1 implies that there is no available n -pair. The only possible 3-prime is of Type 2 but $2^3 \cdot 47 + 1 = 13 \cdot 29$ is composite. This proves:

Theorem 13. *If $P = 47$, then there is no Carmichael number for Case B.*

13. The Impossible Case: $P = 7$

We next deal with the case $P = 7$ in Case B. The combinations of Type 1 primes for $P = 7$ are

$$5 \cdot 17, \quad 5 \cdot 65537, \quad 5 \cdot 17 \cdot 257 \cdot 65537.$$

We have $k_1 = s_1 = 2$, and thus $r_1 = 2^2 \cdot 7^2 + 1 = 197$. Note that $p_2 = 2^{k_2} + 1$ with $k_2 \geq 4$ in all cases. We have $2^4 \mid 2^{k_2} \mid L$. Let

$$m = 5 \cdot 197 \cdot p_2 \prod_{i \geq 1} v_i = (2^3 \cdot 3 \cdot 41 + 1)(2^{k_2} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} v_i,$$

where v_i is a prime of Type 1, 2, or 3, or the product could be empty.

Since $2^4 \mid L$, there must be an n -pair with $n < 3$ or a 3-prime otherwise 3 is the unique 2-power. Since $P = 7 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, we know l_i, s_i are even. Thus, there is no 3-prime. Since we already used 2-primes p_1, r_1 with $k_1 = s_1 = 2$, there is no 2-pair. This proves:

Theorem 14. *If $P = 7$, then there is no Carmichael number for Case B.*

14. Case: $P = 3$ for Case B

The last possible P for Case B is $P = 3$. It follows from Table 7 that the combinations of Type 1 primes for $P = 3$ are

$$5 \cdot 17, \quad 5 \cdot 257, \quad 5 \cdot 65537, \quad 5 \cdot 17 \cdot 257 \cdot 65537.$$

In all cases, we have $k_1 = s_1 = 2$, $k_2 \geq 4$, and thus $r_1 = 2^2 \cdot 3^2 + 1 = 37$ and $2^4 \mid L$.

14.1. Case 1: $17 \mid m$

Let us first consider the case when $17 \mid m$. Let

$$m = 5 \cdot 17 \cdot 37 \prod_{i \geq 1} v_i = (2^3 \cdot 23 + 1)(2^4 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} v_i,$$

where v_i is a prime of Type 1, 2, or 3. By the minimality argument, there is an n -pair $n < 4$ or a 3-prime. From Table 6, we see that there is no such pair and the only 3-prime is 73. Then we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 17 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \prod_{i \geq 2} v_i = (2^4 \cdot 3 \cdot 4783 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 2} v_i.$$

Since there are no 4-primes and possible n -pairs, the product must be empty. But if the product is empty, then m is not a Carmichael number as 3^2 does not divide $m - 1$.

14.2. Case 2: The Type 1 Combination is $5 \cdot 257$

We next consider the case when the Type 1 combination is $5 \cdot 257$. Then

$$m = 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 37 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i = (2^3 \cdot 3 \cdot 7 \cdot 283 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i,$$

where u_i is a prime of Type 2, or 3. Note that $2^8 \mid L$. By the minimality argument, we have the 3-prime 73. So

$$m = 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i = (2^6 \cdot 3 \cdot 18077 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i.$$

If the product is empty, then m is not a Carmichael number as 3^2 does not divide $m - 1$. If the product is nonempty, then since there is no n -pair $n < 6$, there must be a 6-prime. There are two 6-primes from Table 6: 193 and 577.

14.2.1. Subcase 1: $q_1 = 193$

Suppose that $q_1 = 193$. Then we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 193 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i = (2^7 \cdot 3^3 \cdot 13 \cdot 44729 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i.$$

If the product is empty, then m is not a Carmichael number as $2^8 \mid L$ but 2^8 does not divide $m - 1$. By the minimality argument, there is a 7-prime as no possible n -pair exists. The unique 7-prime is 1153. So we have

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 193 \cdot 1153 \prod_{i \geq 4} u_i \\ &= (2^8 \cdot 3^3 \cdot 11 \cdot 10158227 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 4} u_i. \end{aligned}$$

If the product is empty, then

$$m = 5 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 193 \cdot 257 \cdot 1153$$

is a Carmichael number since $L = 2^8 \cdot 3^2$ divides $m - 1 = 2^8 \cdot 3^3 \cdot 11 \cdot 10158227$.

If the product is nonempty, then there must be an 8-prime, which is 769. Then

$$m = 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 193 \cdot 1153 \cdot 769 \prod_{i \geq 5} u_i = (2^9 \cdot 3 \cdot 19 \cdot 20351473151 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 5} u_i.$$

As there is no 9-prime or possible n -pair, the product must be empty. Then m is not a Carmichael number as $3^2 \nmid m - 1$.

14.2.2. Subcase 2: $r_3 = 577$

Suppose now that $r_3 = 577$. Then

$$m = 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 577 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i = (2^{11} \cdot 3 \cdot 325951 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i.$$

If the product is empty, then m is not a Carmichael number as $3^2 \nmid m - 1$. If the product is nonempty, then by the minimality argument with $2^8 \mid L$, there is an n -pair with $n < 8$ or an n -prime with $n = 8, 9, 10, 11$. Looking at Table 6, we see that there is no possible such pair. We have the 8-prime 769 and the 11-prime 18433.

14.2.2.1. Subsubcase 1: 8-prime 769 Suppose that 769 is a divisor of m . Then

$$m = 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 577 \cdot 769 \prod_{i \geq 4} u_i = (2^8 \cdot 3^4 \cdot 283 \cdot 262433 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 4} u_i.$$

If the product is empty, then

$$m = 5 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 257 \cdot 577 \cdot 769$$

is a Carmichael number since $L = 2^8 \cdot 3^2$ divides $m - 1 = 2^8 \cdot 3^4 \cdot 283 \cdot 262433$.

If the product is nonempty, then the minimality argument implies that m has an 8-prime. However, there is no more available 8-primes. Thus, in this case m is not a Carmichael number.

14.2.2.2. Subsubcase 2: 11-prime 18433 Next, suppose that 18433 is a divisor of m . Then

$$m = 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 577 \cdot 18433 \prod_{i \geq 4} u_i = (2^{12} \cdot 3 \cdot 3004127393 \cdot +1) \prod_{i \geq 4} u_i.$$

If the product is empty, then m is not a Carmichael number as $3^2 \nmid m - 1$. If the product is nonempty, then the minimality argument yields that there is an n -prime with $n = 8, 9, 10, 11, 12$. From Table 6, we have the 8-prime 769 and the 12-prime 12289. The former case was already dealt with in the previous case. So, we consider the case $12289 \mid m$. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 577 \cdot 18433 \cdot 12289 \prod_{i \geq 5} u_i \\ &= (2^{13} \cdot 3^2 \cdot 2357 \cdot 2610502159 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 5} u_i. \end{aligned}$$

If the product is empty, then

$$m = 5 \cdot 257 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 577 \cdot 12289 \cdot 18433$$

is a Carmichael number since $L = 2^{12} \cdot 3^2$ divides

$$m - 1 = 2^{13} \cdot 3^2 \cdot 2357 \cdot 2610502159.$$

Suppose that the product is nonempty. Then since $2^{12} \mid L$, by the minimality argument, there must be an n -pair with $n < 11$ or 12-prime or 13-prime. Table 6 shows that this is not the case.

14.3. Case 3: The Type 1 Combination is 5 · 65537

The last case for $P = 3$ in Case B is when the Type 1 combination is $5 \cdot 65537$. Then

$$m = 5 \cdot 65537 \cdot 37 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i = (2^3 \cdot 23 + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i,$$

where u_i is a prime of Type 2 or 3. Note that $2^{16} \mid L$. By the minimality argument, the product cannot be empty, and there must be a 3-prime. The only 3-prime is 73

from Table Table 6. Then

$$m = 5 \cdot 65537 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i = (2^6 \cdot 211 + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i.$$

Again, the product cannot be empty, and there must be a 6-prime. There are two 6-primes: 193 and 577.

14.3.1. Subcase 1: 6-prime is 193

Suppose that $193 \mid m$. Then we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 65537 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 193 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i = (2^7 \cdot 7 \cdot 2909 + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i.$$

Furthermore, the product cannot be empty, and there must be a 7-prime. The only 7-prime is 1153 and we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 65537 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 193 \cdot 1153 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i = (2^9 \cdot 641 \cdot 9157 + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i.$$

And again, by the minimality argument the product is not empty, but there is no 9-prime or admissible pairs.

14.3.2. Subcase 2: 6-prime is 577

Next suppose that $577 \mid m$. Then we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 65537 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 577 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i = (2^8 \cdot 61 \cdot 499 + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i.$$

By the minimality argument, the 8-prime 769 divides m . Then

$$m = 5 \cdot 65537 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 577 \cdot 769 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i = (2^9 \cdot 7^2 \cdot 238853 + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i.$$

There is no 9-prime or admissible pairs. Hence, there is no Carmichael number in this case. In summary, we obtain:

Theorem 15. *Let m be a Carmichael number with $L = 2^\alpha \cdot 3^2$. In Case B ($k_1 = s_1 < l_1$), the following three are all Carmichael numbers of this type:*

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 5 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 193 \cdot 257 \cdot 1153 \\ m &= 5 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 257 \cdot 577 \cdot 769 \\ m &= 5 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 257 \cdot 577 \cdot 12289 \cdot 18433 \end{aligned}$$

15. Case C: $l_1 = s_1 < k_1$

Let m be a Carmichael number with $L = 2^\alpha P^2$ as before. In this section, we consider Case C: $l_1 = s_1 < k_1$. Note that $1 \leq l_1 < k_2$. From Table 1, the possible values for k_1 are 2, 4, 8.

16. Case 1: $k_1 = 2$

Consider the case $k_1 = 2$. Then we must have $l_1 = s_1 = 1$. By Lemma 1, this yields that $P = 3$ as s_1 is odd. Then we have $q_1 = 2 \cdot 3 + 1 = 7$ and $r_1 = 2 \cdot 3^2 + 1 = 19$. From Table 1, the Type 1 combinations for $P = 3$ with $k_1 = 2$ are

$$5 \cdot 17, \quad 5 \cdot 257, \quad 5 \cdot 65537, \quad 5 \cdot 17 \cdot 257 \cdot 65537.$$

In all cases, we have $2^4 \mid L$. Let

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \prod_{i \geq 1} v_i = (2^3 \cdot 83 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} v_i,$$

where v_i is a prime of Type 1, 2, or 3, or it could be empty. As $2^4 \mid L$, by the minimality argument (Theorem 3) there must be a 2-pair or a 3-prime in $\prod_{i \geq 1} v_i$. We see from Table 6 that (13, 37) is the only 2-pair and 73 is the only 3-prime.

16.1. Subcase 1: the 2-pair (13, 37)

Suppose that m has the 2-pair (13, 37). Then

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 \cdot 37 \prod_{i \geq 3} v_i = (2^3 \cdot 39983 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} v_i.$$

By the minimality argument, m has the 3-prime 73. Then

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \prod_{i \geq 3} v_i = (2^7 \cdot 182423 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} v_i.$$

Note that we have used all possible primes with 2-power less than 4 (See Table 6) and 17 is the unique 4-prime. Thus $17 \nmid m$, otherwise 2^4 is the unique smallest power of 2. It follows that $2^8 \mid L$. Hence by the minimality argument, there is either an n -pair with $n < 7$ or a 7-prime. Thus, there are two cases: the 6-pair (193, 577) and the 7-prime 1153.

16.1.1. Subsubcase 1: the 6-pair (193, 577)

Suppose that m has the 6-pair (193, 577). Then we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 193 \cdot 577 \prod_{i \geq 5} v_i = (2^7 \cdot 2003 \cdot 10142191 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 5} v_i.$$

As $2^8 \mid L$, the minimality arguments yields that m has the 7-prime 1153. Then

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 193 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153 \prod_{i \geq 6} v_i \\ &= (2^8 \cdot 1092373 \cdot 10721143 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 6} v_i. \end{aligned}$$

If the product $\prod_{i \geq 6} v_i = 1$, then m is not a Carmichael number because $3^2 \nmid m - 1$. Thus the product is nonempty. As there is no more admissible pairs, there must be a 8-prime. There are two 8-primes: 257 and 769

16.1.1.1. Subsubsubcase 1: the 8-prime: 257 Suppose that $257 \mid m$. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 193 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153 \cdot 257 \prod_{i \geq 7} v_i \\ &= (2^{10} \cdot 3^2 \cdot 83607005432809 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 7} v_i. \end{aligned}$$

If the product is empty, then

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 13 \cdot 19 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 193 \cdot 257 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153$$

is a Carmichael number since $L = 2^8 \cdot 3^2$ divides $m - 1 = 2^{10} \cdot 3^2 \cdot 83607005432809$.

Note that $2^8 \mid L$. If the product is nonempty, then there is an n -prime with $n = 8, 9, 10, 11$ as there is no admissible pair. So m has the 8-prime 769, and then

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 193 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153 \cdot 257 \cdot 769 \prod_{i \geq 7} v_i \\ &= (2^8 \cdot 3 \cdot 11 \cdot 31 \cdot 2262537965202233 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 7} v_i. \end{aligned}$$

Since there is no more admissible pair or 8-prime, the product is empty, but then m is not a Carmichael number as $3^2 \nmid m - 1$.

16.1.1.2. Subsubsubcase 2: the 8-prime: 769 Next, suppose that $769 \mid m$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 193 \cdot 577 \cdot 1153 \cdot 769 \prod_{i \geq 7} v_i \\ &= (2^9 \cdot 4503066806229347 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 7} v_i. \end{aligned}$$

If the product is empty, then m is not a Carmichael number as $3 \nmid m - 1$. Then by the minimality argument, there is an 8-prime or a 9-prime. Since there is no 9-prime, m must have the 8-prime 257. Then this case reduces to the previous case.

16.1.2. Subsubcase 2: the 7-prime 1153

Now suppose that $r_4 = 1153 \mid m$. Then

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 1153 \cdot 577 \prod_{i \geq 5} v_i = (2^{12} \cdot 11 \cdot 597539 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 5} v_i.$$

Since $2^8 \mid L$, by the minimality argument, there is an n -prime with $8 \leq n \leq 12$. Those are 8-primes 769, 257, the 11-prime 18433, and the 12-prime 12289 from Table 6.

16.1.2.1. Subsubsubcase 1: the 8-prime 769 When $769 \mid m$, we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 1153 \cdot 577 \cdot 769 \prod_{i \geq 6} v_i = (2^8 \cdot 89 \cdot 1483 \cdot 612737 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 6} v_i.$$

If the product is empty, then m is not a Carmichael number as $3 \nmid m - 1$. Thus it has the 8-prime 257, and then

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 1153 \cdot 577 \cdot 769 \cdot 257 \prod_{i \geq 7} v_i \\ &= (2^{10} \cdot 3^2 \cdot 61 \cdot 9464682529 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 6} v_i. \end{aligned}$$

The product must be empty since there is no n -prime for $n = 8, 9, 10$. Then

$$\boxed{m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 13 \cdot 19 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 257 \cdot 577 \cdot 769 \cdot 1153}$$

is a Carmichael number since $L = 2^8 \cdot 3^2$ divides $m - 1$.

16.1.2.2. Subsubsubcase 2: the 8-prime 257 When $257 \mid m$, we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 1153 \cdot 577 \cdot 257 \prod_{i \geq 6} v_i = (2^8 \cdot 3 \cdot 43 \cdot 209518481 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 6} v_i.$$

If the product is empty, then m is not a Carmichael number as $3^2 \nmid m - 1$. Thus m has the 8-prime 769, and this case reduces to the previous case.

16.1.2.3. Subsubsubcase 3: the 11-prime 18433 If $18433 \mid m$, then

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 1153 \cdot 577 \cdot 257 \cdot 18433 \prod_{i \geq 6} v_i = (2^{11}x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 6} v_i,$$

where x is an odd number. (From now on, to save space, I use x for an odd number, especially when m is not a Carmichael number.) Note that $2^{11} \mid L$ but there is no more 11-prime. Thus the product must be empty. If the product is empty, then m is not a Carmichael number since $3^2 \nmid m - 1$.

16.1.2.4. Subsubsubcase 4: 12-prime 12289 When $12289 \mid m$, we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 1153 \cdot 577 \cdot 257 \cdot 12289 \prod_{i \geq 6} v_i = (2^{14}x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 6} v_i.$$

Since $2^{12} \mid L$, there is an n -prime with $n = 12, 13, 14$. From Table 6, such a prime must be the 14-prime 147457. Then

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \cdot 1153 \cdot 577 \cdot 257 \cdot 12289 \cdot 147457 \prod_{i \geq 7} v_i = (2^{15}x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 7} v_i$$

and $2^{14} \mid L$. Since there is no 14-prime and 15-prime, the product must be empty. But then m is not a Carmichael number as $3 \nmid m - 1$.

16.2. Subcase 2: the 3-prime 73

Next, we consider the case $r_2 = 73$ with $s_2 = 3$. Then

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 73 \prod_{i \geq 2} v_i = (2^5 \cdot 37 \cdot 41 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 2} v_i,$$

Since $2^4 \mid L$, by the minimality argument, there must be either the 2-pair (13, 37) or an n -prime with $n = 4, 5$. The former was already considered in Section 16.1. From Table 6, there are the 4-prime 17 and 5-prime 97.

16.2.1. Subsubcase 1: the 4-prime 17

When $17 \mid m$, we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 73 \cdot 17 \prod_{i \geq 3} v_i = (2^4 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 11 \cdot 521 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} v_i,$$

Since there is no more 4-prime, the product is empty. Then

$$\boxed{m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 17 \cdot 19 \cdot 73}$$

is a Carmichael number since $L = 2^4 \cdot 3^2$ divides $m - 1$.

16.2.2. Subsubcase 2: the 5-prime 97

When $97 \mid m$, we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 73 \cdot 97 \prod_{i \geq 3} v_i = (2^9 \cdot 17 \cdot 541 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} v_i.$$

If the product is empty, then m is not a Carmichael number as $3 \nmid m - 1$. Since $2^5 \mid L$, by the minimality argument, there is an n -prime with $n = 5, 6, 7, 8$. From Table 6, there are five possible such prime numbers: 6-primes 193, 577, the 7-prime 1153, and 8-primes 769, 257. We consider these cases individually below.

Convention: We use x for an odd number such that $2^a x + 1$ is not a Carmichael number.

16.2.2.1. Subsubsubcase 1: 6-primes 193 When $193 \mid m$, then

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 73 \cdot 97 \cdot 193 \prod_{i \geq 4} v_i = (2^6 x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 4} v_i.$$

Our convention is that x is an odd number and $2^6 x + 1$ is not a Carmichael number. By the minimality argument, the 6-prime 577 must be used. Then

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 73 \cdot 97 \cdot 193 \cdot 577 \prod_{i \geq 5} v_i = (2^8 x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 5} v_i.$$

Since $2^6 \mid L$, the possible values for v_6 are the 7-prime 1153 and 8-primes 769, 257.

16.2.2.1.1. Case 1153 $\mid m$ When $1153 \mid m$, we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 73 \cdot 97 \cdot 193 \cdot 577 \cdot 1152 \prod_{i \geq 6} v_i = (2^7 x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 6} v_i.$$

There is no other 7-prime. No Carmichael number exists in this case.

16.2.2.1.2. Case 769 $\mid m$ When $769 \mid m$, we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 73 \cdot 97 \cdot 193 \cdot 577 \cdot 769 \prod_{i \geq 6} v_i = (2^{12} x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 6} v_i.$$

Note that $2^8 \mid L$. There must be an n -prime with $n = 8, 9, 10, 11, 12$. From Table 6, these are the 8-prime 257, the 11-prime 18433, and the 12-prime 12289.

1. When $257 \mid m$, we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 73 \cdot 97 \cdot 193 \cdot 577 \cdot 769 \cdot 257 \prod_{i \geq 7} v_i = (2^8 x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 7} v_i$$

and there is no further 8-prime. No Carmichael number exists in this case.

2. When $18433 \mid m$, we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 73 \cdot 97 \cdot 193 \cdot 577 \cdot 769 \cdot 18433 \prod_{i \geq 7} v_i = (2^{11} x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 7} v_i.$$

Note that $2^{11} \mid L$ and there is no 11-prime. No Carmichael number exists in this case.

3. When $12289 \mid m$.

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 73 \cdot 97 \cdot 193 \cdot 577 \cdot 769 \cdot 12289 \prod_{i \geq 7} v_i = (2^{14} x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 7} v_i.$$

Note that $2^{12} \mid L$. So m must have an n -prime with $n = 12, 13, 14$. Table 6 gives the 14-prime 147457. Then combining this number yields

$$m = (2^{16}x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 8} v_i.$$

Since $2^{14} \mid L$, there is an n -prime with $n = 14, 15, 16$. Table 6 gives the 16-prime 65537. Then including this factor, we have

$$m = (2^{17}x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 9} v_i.$$

Since $2^{16} \mid L$, we must have the 17-prime 1179649. This gives

$$m = (2^{18}x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 10} v_i.$$

Furthermore, m is divisible by the 18-prime 786433. Then m is

$$\begin{aligned} &5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 73 \cdot 97 \cdot 193 \cdot 577 \cdot 769 \cdot 12289 \cdot 147457 \cdot 65537 \cdot 1179649 \cdot 786433 \prod_{i \geq 11} v_i \\ &= (2^{23} \cdot 3^3 \cdot 13 \cdot 14783 \cdot 1020702401040725135124085171 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 11} v_i \end{aligned}$$

Since there is no more n -prime for $18 \leq n \leq 23$, the product must be empty. Then

$$\boxed{5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 73 \cdot 97 \cdot 193 \cdot 577 \cdot 769 \cdot 12289 \cdot 147457 \cdot 65537 \cdot 1179649 \cdot 786433}$$

is a Carmichael number since $L = 2^{18} \cdot 3^2$ divides $m - 1$.

16.2.2.1.3. Case 257 | m When $257 \mid m$, we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 73 \cdot 97 \cdot 193 \cdot 577 \cdot 257 \prod_{i \geq 6} v_i = (2^9x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 6} v_i.$$

Since $2^8 \mid L$, there is an n -prime with $n = 8, 9$. As there is no 9-prime in Table 6, we have the 8-prime 769. Combining the number 769, we have

$$m = (2^8x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 7} v_i.$$

As there is no more 8-prime, no Carmichael number exists in this case.

16.2.2.2. Subsubsubcase 2: the 6-prime 577 When $577 \mid m$, we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 73 \cdot 97 \cdot 577 \prod_{i \geq 4} v_i = (2^6x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 4} v_i.$$

Since $2^6 \mid L$, m is divisible by the 6-prime 193. Then this reduces to the case dealt in Section 16.2.2.1.

16.2.2.3. Subsubsubcase 3: the 7-prime 1153 When $1153 \mid m$, we have

$$m = (2^7x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 4} v_i.$$

Since $2^7 \mid L$ but there is no 7-prime, no Carmichael number exists in this case.

16.2.2.4. Subsubsubcase 4: the 8-prime 769 When $769 \mid m$, we have

$$m = (2^8x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 4} v_i.$$

Since $2^8 \mid L$, the 8-prime 257 divides m . Then including 257, we have

$$m = (2^9x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 5} v_i.$$

As there is no more 8-prime and 9-prime, no Carmichael number exists in this case.

16.2.2.5. Subsubsubcase 5: the 8-prime 257 When $257 \mid m$, we have

$$m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 73 \cdot 97 \cdot 257 \prod_{i \geq 4} v_i = (2^8 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 23 \cdot 41 \cdot 557 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 4} v_i.$$

If the product is empty, then

$$\boxed{m = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 73 \cdot 97 \cdot 257}$$

is a Carmichael number since $L = 2^8 \cdot 3^2$ divides $m - 1$. Otherwise, since $2^8 \mid L$, the 8-prime 769 divides m , and

$$m = (2^9x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 5} v_i.$$

As there is no more 8-prime and 9-prime, no other Carmichael number exists in this case.

17. Case 2: $k_1 = 4$

We consider the case $k_1 = 4$ in Case C. We have three cases to consider: $l_1 = s_1 = 1, 2, 3$.

17.1. $l_1 = s_1 = 1$

Suppose that $l_1 = s_1 = 1$. Since s_1 is odd, we must have $P = 3$ by Lemma 1. So $q_1 = 7$ and $r_1 = 19$.

There are two combinations of Type 1 primes: $17 \cdot 257$ and $17 \cdot 65537$ from Table 1. In either case, we have $2^4 \mid L$.

Let

$$m = 17 \cdot (2^{k_2} + 1) \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i = (2^2 \cdot 5 \cdot 113 + 1)(2^{k_2} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i,$$

where u_i is a prime of Type 2 or 3 and k_2 is either 4 or 16.

By the minimality argument (Theorem 3), there must be a 2-prime: $q_1 = 13$ or $r_2 = 37$.

17.1.1. Subcase 1: the 2-prime 13

When $13 \mid m$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 17 \cdot (2^{k_2} + 1) \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i \\ &= (2^4 \cdot 11 \cdot 167 + 1)(2^{k_2} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i \\ &= (2^4 x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i \end{aligned}$$

for both values of k_2 . Here we use the same convention of x as before: x is an odd number and $2^4 x + 1$ is not a Carmichael number. Since $2^4 \mid L$ and there is no more 4-prime and n -pair with $n < 4$, no Carmichael number exists in this case.

17.1.2. Subcase 2: the 2-prime 37

Suppose that $37 \mid m$. Then

$$m = 17 \cdot (2^{k_2} + 1) \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 37 \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i = (2^3 \cdot 10457 + 1)(2^{k_2} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i$$

By the minimality argument, there is a 3-prime: 73. So we have

$$m = 17 \cdot (2^{k_2} + 1) \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 37 \cdot 73 \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i = (2^4 x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i$$

for both values of k_2 . Since there is no 4-prime, no Carmichael number exists in this case.

17.2. $l_1 = s_1 = 2$

We now consider the case $l_1 = s_1 = 2$ in Case C. As l_1 is even, this implies that either $P = 3$ or $P \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ by Lemma 1.

17.2.1. Case: $P = 3$

Suppose that $P = 3$. Then we have $q_1 = 13$ and $r_1 = 37$. Then Type 1 prime combinations are either $17 \cdot 257$ or $17 \cdot 65537$ from Table 1. In either case, we have $2^4 \mid L$. Let

$$m = 17 \cdot (2^{k_2} + 1) \cdot 13 \cdot 37 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i,$$

where u_i is a prime of Type 2 or 3. Here k_2 is either 4 or 16. Then we compute

$$m = (2^4x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i$$

for both values of k_2 . Since $2^4 \mid L$, the minimality argument (Theorem 3) implies that the product has either an n -pair with $n < 4$ or a 4-prime. Table 6 shows that this is not the case.

17.2.2. Case: $P \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$

Let $P \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. From Table 1, we find primes $P \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ with $k_1 = 4$ such that $2^2P + 1$ and $2^2P^2 + 1$ are both prime. See Table 8. The values of such P are

Table 8: Possible $P \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ with $l_1 = s_1 = 2, k_1 = 4$

P	$2^2 \cdot P + 1$	$2^2 \cdot P^2 + 1$	Type 1 prime combination
7	29 prime	197 prime	$17 \cdot 257$
13	53 prime	677 prime	$17 \cdot 257$
43	173 prime	×	
127	509 prime	×	
2579	×	×	

×=composite

$P = 7$ and $P = 13$.

17.2.2.1. Subcase 1: $P = 7$ When $P = 7$, we have $q_1 = 29$ and $r_1 = 197$. The only Type 1 combination for $P = 7$ is $17 \cdot 257$.

Let

$$m = 17 \cdot 257 \cdot 29 \cdot 197 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i = (2^5 \cdot 3^3 \cdot 7 \cdot 4127 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i,$$

where u_i is a Type 2 or 3 prime. Note that $2^8 \mid L$.

By the minimality argument, there must be an n -pair with $n < 5$ or a 5-prime. However this is impossible from Table 3. (Recall that l_i, s_i are even as $P \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$.) No Carmichael number exists in this case.

17.2.2.2. Subcase 1: $P = 13$ When $P = 13$, we have $q_1 = 53$, and $r_1 = 677$. The only Type 1 combination is $17 \cdot 257$. Note that $2^8 \mid L$. Let

$$m = 17 \cdot 257 \cdot 53 \cdot 677 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i = (2^3 \cdot 293 \cdot 79813 + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i.$$

where u_i is a Type 2 or 3 prime. By the minimality argument, there must be a 3-prime but since l_i, s_i are even as $13 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, there is no 3-prime. No Carmichael number exists in this case.

17.3. $l_1 = s_1 = 3$

If $l_1 = s_1 = 3$, then $P = 3$ since s_1 is odd by Lemma 1. However, $2^3 \cdot 3 + 1 = 5^2$ is not a prime. Hence no Carmichael number exists in this case.

18. Case 3: $k_1 = 8$

We consider the case $l_1 = s_1 < k_1 = 8$. There are seven cases according to the value of $l_1 = 1, 2, \dots, 7$. Note that $257 \cdot 65537$ is the unique Type 1 combination with $k_1 = 8$.

18.1. Subcase 1: $l_1 = s_1 = 1$

When $l_1 = s_1 = 1$, as s_1 is odd, we must have $P = 3$. Then $q_1 = 7$ and $r_1 = 19$. Let

$$m = 257 \cdot 65537 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i = (2^2 \cdot 3 \cdot 11 + 1) \cdot 257 \cdot 65537 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i,$$

where u_i is a Type 2 or 3 prime. Note that $2^{16} \mid L$.

By the minimality argument (Theorem 3) we must have a 2-prime. Then we have either $q_2 = 13$ or $r_2 = 37$. (See Table 6.)

18.1.1. Subsubcase 1: $q_2 = 13$

When $13 \mid m$, then we have

$$m = 257 \cdot 65537 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i = (2^6 \cdot 3^3 + 1) \cdot 257 \cdot 65537 \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i.$$

Since $2^{16} \mid L$, there is an n -pair with $n < 6$ or a 6-prime. We see from Table 6 that there is no such pair and we have two 6-primes: 193 and 577.

18.1.1.1. When $q_3 = 193$ When $193 \mid m$, we have

$$m = 257 \cdot 65537 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 \cdot 193 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i = (2^8 x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i.$$

As there is no admissible pair, we have the 8-prime 769. Combining 769, we have

$$m = (2^{13} x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 4} u_i.$$

As there is no admissible pairs and 13-primes, no Carmichael number exists in this case.

18.1.1.2. When $r_2 = 577$ If $577 \mid m$, then

$$m = 257 \cdot 65537 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 \cdot 577 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i = (2^9 x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i$$

There is no n -pair with $n < 9$ and there is no 9-prime. Hence no Carmichael number exists in this case.

18.1.2. Subsubcase 2: $r_2 = 37$

When $37 \mid m$, then we have

$$m = 257 \cdot 65537 \cdot 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 37 \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i = (2^3 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 41 + 1) \cdot 257 \cdot 65537 \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i.$$

As $2^{16} \mid L$, m is divisible by the 3-prime 73. Combining this yields

$$m = (2^6 x + 1) \cdot 257 \cdot 65537 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i.$$

Hence we have a 6-prime: 193, 577.

18.1.2.1. When $q_2 = 193$ When $193 \mid m$, combining this we have

$$m = (2^8 x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 4} u_i.$$

Then we have the 8-prime 769, and

$$m = (2^{12} x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 5} u_i,$$

which implies again that the 12-prime 12289 divides m . Hence

$$m = (2^{13} x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 6} u_i,$$

but there is no 13-prime. Thus no Carmichael number exists in this case.

18.1.2.2. When $r_4 = 577$ When $577 \mid m$, we combine this and obtain

$$m = (2^7x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 4} u_i.$$

Hence we have the 7-prime 1153 and

$$m = (2^8x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 5} u_i,$$

which implies the existence of the 8-prime 769. Then

$$m = (2^9x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 5} u_i,$$

but there is no 9-prime. Hence no Carmichael number exists in this case.

18.2. Subcase 2: $l_1 = s_1 = 2$

Consider the case $l_1 = s_1 = 2$. As l_1 is even, $P = 3$ or $P \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$.

18.2.1. Subsubcase 1: When $P = 3$

When $P = 3$, we have $q_1 = 13$ and $r_1 = 37$. Note that $2^{16} \mid L$. Then we have by the minimality argument

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 257 \cdot 65537 \cdot 13 \cdot 37 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i \\ &= (2^5 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 + 1)257 \cdot 65537 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i && \text{then the 5-prime 97 divides } m \\ &= (2^6 \cdot 3^6 + 1)57 \cdot 65537 \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i. \end{aligned}$$

This implies that m is divisible by a 6-prime: 193, 577.

18.2.1.1. the 6-prime 193 When $193 \mid m$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} m &= (2^{11}x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i && \text{then the 11-prime 18433 divides } m \\ &= (2^{12}x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 4} u_i && \text{then the 12-prime 12289 divides } m \\ &= (2^{13}x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 5} u_i. \end{aligned}$$

(There were no admissible pairs to consider.) Since there is no 13-prime, no Carmichael number exists in this case.

18.2.1.2. the 6-prime 577 When $577 \mid m$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 257 \cdot 65537 \cdot 13 \cdot 37 \cdot 97 \cdot 577 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i \\ &= (2^7x + 1) \cdot 257 \cdot 65537 \prod_{i \geq 4} u_i && \text{then the 7-prime 1153 divides } m \\ &= (2^9x + 1)(2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 4} u_i \end{aligned}$$

(There were no admissible pairs to consider.) Since there is no 9-prime, no Carmichael number exists in this case.

18.2.2. Subsubcase 2: When $P \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$

Suppose that $P \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. Then the only possible P are 7, 13, 241. However, as $2^2 \cdot 241 + 1 = 5 \cdot 193$ is not prime, there are two cases: $P = 7$ and $P = 13$.

18.2.2.1. When $P = 7$ When $P = 7$, we have $q_1 = 29$ and $r_1 = 197$. Note that $2^{16} \mid L$. Then the minimality arguments (see Table 3) gives

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 257 \cdot 65537 \cdot 29 \cdot 197 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i \\ &= (2^4x + 1) \cdot 257 \cdot 65537 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i && \text{then the 4-prime 113 divides } m \\ &= (2^6x + 1) \cdot 257 \cdot 65537 \prod_{i \geq 2} u_i \end{aligned}$$

and m is divisible by a 6-prime: 449, 3137.

1. When $449 \mid m$, we have

$$m = (2^7x + 1) \cdot 257 \cdot 65537 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i$$

but there is no 7-prime.

2. When $3137 \mid m$, we have

$$m = (2^9x + 1) \cdot 257 \cdot 65537 \prod_{i \geq 3} u_i$$

but there is no 9-prime.

Hence no Carmichael number exists in this case.

18.2.2.2. When $P = 13$ When $P = 13$, then $q_1 = 53$ and $r_1 = 677$. Then we have

$$m = 257 \cdot 65537 \cdot 53 \cdot 677 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i = (2^3x + 1) \cdot 257 \cdot 65537 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i$$

Since l_2, s_2 are even, there is no 3-prime. Hence no Carmichael number exists in this case.

18.3. Subcase 3: $l_1 = s_1 = 3$

When $l_1 = s_1 = 3$, we have $P = 3$ by Lemma 6. But $2^3 \cdot 3 + 1 = 5^2$ is not prime. Hence no Carmichael number exists in this case.

18.4. Subcase 4: $l_1 = s_1 = 4$

When $l_1 = s_1 = 4$, we have either $P = 3$ or $P \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. As $2^4 \cdot 3 + 1 = 7^2$ is not prime, $P \neq 3$. There are three values for $P \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ with $k_1 = 8$: $P = 7, 13, 241$. However, $2^4 \cdot 7^2 + 1 = 5 \cdot 157$, $2^4 \cdot 13 + 1 = 11 \cdot 19$ and $2^4 \cdot 241 + 1 = 7 \cdot 19 \cdot 29$ are not prime. Hence there is no possible P in this case.

18.5. Subcase 5: $l_1 = s_1 = 5$

Consider the case $l_1 = s_1 = 5$. As s_1 is odd, $P = 3$. However $2^5 \cdot 3 + 1 = 17^2$ is not prime. Hence we have no Carmichael number in this case.

18.6. Subcase 6: $l_1 = s_1 = 6$

Suppose $l_1 = s_1 = 6$. As l_1 is even, we have either $P = 3$ or $P \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$.

18.6.1. When $P = 3$

Suppose that $P = 3$. Then $q_1 = 2^6 \cdot 3 + 1 = 193$ and $r_1 = 2^6 \cdot 3^2 + 1 = 577$. Recall that $2^{16} \mid L$. Then we have

$$m = 257 \cdot 65537 \cdot 193 \cdot 577 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i = (2^{10}x + 1) \cdot (2^{16} + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i$$

There is no n -pair with $6 < n < 10$ and there is no 10-prime (See Table 6). Hence no Carmichael number exists in this case by the minimality argument.

18.6.2. When $P \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$

Consider the case $P \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. Then $P = 7, 13, 241$. However $2^6 \cdot 13 + 1 = 7^2 \cdot 17$ and $2^6 \cdot 241 + 1 = 5^2 \cdot 617$ are not prime.

When $P = 7$, we have $q_1 = 449$ and $r_1 = 3137$. Then

$$m = 257 \cdot 65537 \cdot 449 \cdot 3137 \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i = (2^8 x + 1) \prod_{i \geq 1} u_i$$

As there is no n -pair with $6 < n < 8$ and 8-prime (see Table 3), there is no Carmichael number in this case.

18.7. Subcase 7: $l_1 = s_1 = 7$

If $l_1 = s_1 = 7$, then $P = 3$ as s_1 is odd. However, $2^7 \cdot 3 + 1 = 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 11$ is not prime. Thus, no Carmichael number exists in this case by the minimality argument.

This exhausted all the cases, and this completes the proof of Theorem 1.

Acknowledgement. I would like to show my gratitude to Samuel Wagstaff for his suggestion to extend the result of Wright and for his valuable comments. I would also like to thank Byron Heersink for many helpful conversations. Finally, I would like to thank an anonymous referee for his/her valuable comments which helped to improve the manuscript.

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